

possess intermediate AC, GT, and GC. WT, one of the key selection indices for high grain yield, ranged from 7.5 to 42.2 g. Milled rice KL ranged from 3.20 to 8.06 mm, and KB ranged from very thin (1.38 mm) to very thick (3.08) mm. Based on the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations' milled rice scale, the varieties were grouped as long-slender (110), medium-slender (9), long-bold (82), medium-bold (19), short-bold (33), short-round (42), and medium (63).

High volume expansion after cooking (maximum linear KE with minimum breadthwise expansion) is one of the characters of basmati rice. Varieties that double their length with cooking are preferred. KE range was wide among the varieties (Table 1).

We determined the Pearson's correlation coefficients for eight quality

indices. AC showed highly significant negative correlation with all the traits except LB (0.10) and KE (0.19). WT had significant negative correlation with AC and KE, suggesting that lower grain weight types must be selected to identify basmati types. The association between KE and KL as well as LB was negative and significant, indicating that many of the slender grains do not

elongate after cooking. KE had a significant positive association with AC, while that with GT was significant and negative. Most of the aromatic varieties with greater linear KE also have intermediate AC and GT.

Among the aromatic germplasm evaluated, 39 accessions are basmati based on grain shape and elongation; details are provided for nine (Table 2).

Table 2. Some typical Basmati varieties and their grain and cooking quality characteristics.^a

Variety	Origin	AC	GT	GC	KL	KB	LB	KE
Barah	Afghanistan	17.6	4.58	70	7.55	1.88	4.02	2.18
MussaTarom	Iran	19.2	4.20	40	7.62	1.88	4.05	1.83
Mulai	Iran	19.5	3.58	55	7.76	1.96	3.96	1.93
Sadri	Iran	18.2	4.54	35	7.66	1.94	3.45	2.10
Pakistani Fine	Pakistan	20.4	5.40	50	6.96	1.96	3.55	1.93
Sathi Basmati	India	18.4	3.83	58	7.24	1.92	3.78	1.95
Basmati 370	India	21.0	3.83	57	6.84	1.84	3.72	2.10
KarnalLocal	India	21.2	3.66	60	7.06	1.90	3.72	1.85
Hansraj	India	18.1	4.50	60	6.88	1.94	3.55	2.17

^a AC = amylose content, GT = gelatinization temperature, GC = gel consistency, KL = kernel length, KB = kernel breadth, LB = length-breadth ratio, KE = kernel elongation.

Biochemical composition of principal components of rice seeds

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Rice is an important source of carbohydrates in the diets of several Nigerian populations, especially in the forest belt. We determined the nutritional

values of rough rice, unpolished rice, polished rice, hulls, bran, and rice mill feed for rice grown in Nigeria.

Rice components were collected from the rice mill of the College of Agriculture, Enugu State University, Abakaliki Campus, Nigeria, ground, and then mixed to obtain homogeneous samples. The methods of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists were used to determine moisture,

crude protein, ash, crude fiber, crude fat, dry matter, and nitrogen free extract. Calorific values were calculated by multiplying the mean values of crude protein, fat, fiber, and nitrogen free extracts by Atwater factors.

The mineral composition was assayed for each sample in 5 N HCl and then analyzed with a Perkin-Elmer atomic absorption spectrophotometer and flame photometry method.

Chemical composition of the principal nutritional components of rice grown in Nigeria.

Constituent	Composition (%) ^a						
	Rough rice	Unpolished rice	Polished rice	Rice hulls	Rice bran	Rice mill feed	Rice starch refuse
<i>Proximate composition (n=3)</i>							
Moisture	12.3 ± 0.4	12.3 ± 0.2	10.8 ± 0.1	11.4 ± 0.2	11.2 ± 0.2	6.1 ± 0.3	9.1 ± 1.0
Dry matter	87.7 ± 0.1	87.8 ± 0.4	89.2 ± 0.7	88.6 ± 0.4	88.9 ± 0.5	93.9 ± 3.3	90.9 ± 0.2
Ash	6.4 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.1	17.2 ± 1.0	10.8 ± 0.3	15.9 ± 2.8	2.1 ± 0.1
Crude protein	9.6 ± 0.0	9.1 ± 0.6	8.4 ± 0.4	3.4 ± 0.2	12.0 ± 0.4	6.9 ± 1.2	9.9 ± 0.9
Crude fat	1.7 ± 0.5	1.1 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.2	15.1 ± 0.4	4.8 ± 0.7	0.9 ± 0.0
Crude fiber	11.1 ± 0.8	0.5 ± 0.5	0.2 ± 0.0	34.7 ± 1.6	8.7 ± 1.2	27.9 ± 6.8	1.9 ± 0.0
Nitrogen free extract	58.9 ± 1.8	75.0 ± 1.0	78.1 ± 0.4	32.7 ± 1.1	42.2 ± 1.5	38.5 ± 4.5	78.2 ± 0.9
Calorific value (kcal 100 g ⁻¹)	334.1	348.5	355.2	288.5	387.6	336.2	388.1
<i>Mineral content (n=3)</i>							
Calcium	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0
Phosphorus	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	1.7 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0

^aValues are means ± standard deviations of three replications.

Moisture content was moderate among the different samples (see table). The percentage of ash was larger in rice hulls (17.2%), rice mill feed (15.9%), and rice bran (10.8%) than in other samples; it was lowest in polished rice (1.6%). All principal components were good sources of crude protein except rice hulls (3.4%), and all were low in crude

fat except for rice bran (15.1%). Crude fiber was greatest for rice hulls (34.7%) and rice mill feed (27.9%) and moderately low for rough rice (11.1%) and rice bran (8.7%). The different components had relatively high calorific values and were identical in inorganic element, calcium, and phosphorus contents. ■

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

Pest resistance

Activity of the promoter of a rice lipid transfer protein gene in transgenic rice

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Scientists have assumed that plant lipid transfer proteins (*Ltp*) participate in membrane biogenesis, which facilitates the movement of lipids between membranes. Expression analysis of these genes revealed complex patterns characterized by high cell and tissue specificity. Homologous or heterologous transfer of translational *Ltp* promoter-*gus* fusions in transgenic plants should facilitate localization of that expression. Recently, Kalla et al (1994) described aleurone cell-specific activity of the promoter of the barley *Ltp2* gene in transgenic rice. We report here activity of the promoter of a rice *Ltp* gene—a member of a small multigenic family—in transgenic rice.

A construct bearing a translational fusion between the promoter region of a rice lipid transfer protein (*Ltp*) gene (Vignols et al 1994), the *uidA* coding sequence, and the nos 3' terminator

(p Δ Gus1177) was transferred along with a plasmid consisting of the *bar* gene driven by the 35S promoter (p35SAc, Hoechst, Germany) to haploid, microspore callus cell suspension protoplasts in four separate experiments of PEG-mediated transformation, as described in Chair et al (1995).

Transient activity of the *Ltp* promoter quantified using the fluorimetric GUS assay 48 h after transformation was not significantly different from that of control protoplasts. However, protoplasts treated with the pEMUGN plasmid (Last et al 1991) exhibited very high GUS activity, suggesting that the *Ltp* promoter is not active in unorganized, undifferentiated cells.

The four experiments yielded 274 ammonium glufosinate-resistant calli that regenerated 136 plants. Histochemical assay of protoplast-derived colonies revealed faint GUS activity in some calli. Histochemical assay of 103 out of 136 regenerated plants enabled us to detect GUS activity in 47 plants, suggesting that the cotransformation efficiency reached at least 45%. The *Ltp* promoter appeared more active in the innermost developing leaves and variation in intensity of staining was noted among the plants. No GUS activity was found in the roots of plants exhibiting GUS-positive leaves. Southern blot analysis of 13 plants confirmed integration of both *uidA* and *bar* genes in the genome of regenerated plants (see figure).

Histological localization of GUS activity in transverse sections of shoots

of these plants permitted us to detect GUS activity in all cell types of the first innermost leaf, whereas that activity appeared localized in the outer epidermis and subepidermis of the second innermost leaf. In leaves of higher rank, activity became restricted to the outer epidermal cell layer. In fully mature leaves, GUS activity was mainly detected in stomate guard cells and in vascular bundles.

Southern blot analyses of 8 T₀ plants regenerated from protoplasts treated with the p Δ Gus1177 plasmid and exhibiting GUS activity in leaves. Genomic DNA was digested by *Bam*HI, which cuts the plasmid once, resolved in a 0.8% agarose gel, transferred to a nylon membrane, and then probed with an internal 1.8-kb fragment corresponding to the *gus* coding sequence. UT= DNA from an untransformed plant. The expected position of 5.9-kb fragments corresponding to tandem insertions of the plasmid is marked with an arrow.